

Management

PROFESSIONAL TEACHER MANAGEMENT IN EFFECTIVE SCHOOLS

Sumarto ¹, Emmi Kholilah Harahap ²

¹ Postgraduate Lecturer in IAIN Curup - Indonesia

² Lecturer in STAI Ma'arif Jambi - Indonesia

Abstract

Professional teacher management in effective schools. This paper conveys the importance of applying professional teacher management to realize effective schools. There is no good school, if it does not have professional teachers who are able to manage the learning process well in the classroom, start the planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating processes.

The method used in this paper is literature study, tracing some references relating to effective management, teachers and schools. There are several findings of the author about professional teacher management including professional teachers, namely: having a commitment to organizational culture or commitment to the learning process of students; mastering in-depth subject matter and how to teach it; able to think systematically about what is done and learn from experience; and is a part of learning societies from their professional environment that enables them to improve their professionalism, so that it becomes an important indicator in creating an effective school.

Keywords: Management; Professional Teachers; Effective Schools.

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1. Introduction

The existence of management in an institution is very important. Because in management it covers all aspects of management and regulation in an institution, especially educational institutions in which there are many people. Educational institutions such as school education institutions are formal institutions that are very strategic to develop thinking (science), opinions and most importantly, are able to develop and improve human resources (student resources) itself maximally. School education institutions also consist of a collection of intelligent people, such as school principals, education staff (Teachers), education staff (administrators), students (students) and even to the school guards (security). All of them unite to build their institution into a professional, developed and developing educational (school) institution.

Developing educational institutions is one of the main tasks and responsibilities of the principal as a manager. The task must be carried out optimally, planned and directed by the school principal and by the education staff in the school. Because if an educational institution develops, is advanced and is well-known, then the school will be attracted and attracted by many people (the community). And of course it will affect the school input. A lot of input is one indicator that the school is progressing and developing. The development of educational institutions is also inseparable from the role of professional teachers and management of school relations with the community.

This paper will explain how professional teacher management builds a good culture in every activity in the school. Because with the role of professional teachers in changing patterns of habits that exist in schools, so that new patterns emerge that are better patterns that become effective schools.

2. Discussion

2.1. Professional Teacher Management

Management comes from the word to manage which means to manage. According to Ricchard, The Management of the attainment of organizational goals in an effective and efficient manner through planning, organizing, leading, and controlling organizational organizational results. Management is the achievement of organizational goals in effective and efficient planning, organizing, leading, and controlling organizational resources.

In line with what Arikunto explained that: Educational management is an activity or series of activities in the form of a collaborative management business process of a group of people who are members of an educational organization to achieve educational goals that have been previously determined to be effective and efficient. Likewise, Usman means that management can also be defined as the process of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling educational resources to achieve educational goals effectively and efficiently.

George R. Terry, in his book Malayu Hasibuan, provides management definition as follows: "Management is a distinct process consisting of planning, organizing, acting, and controlling, performed to determine and accomplished stated objects by the use of human being and other resource". (Management is a process that consists of planning, organizing, mobilizing and supervising which is carried out to achieve the stated goals using human resources and other resources). Made Pidarta explained management was defined as an activity of integrating educational resources so that they were centralized in achieving predetermined educational goals. Teachers are educators who have a strategic role in development in the field of national education. In connection with the description above. According to Mulyasa, there are three conditions that must be considered in the development of education in order to contribute to improving the quality of human resources, namely: (1) teachers and professional education staff; (2) building facilities; and (3) quality books. So, professional teachers are the main requirements that must be met so that education can successfully realize national education goals. The Directorate of Education Personnel explains that the teacher is an element of education that is very closely related to students, in their daily education efforts at school and many determine the success of students in achieving their goals.

With regard to professional teachers, in articles 8 and 9 of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers it is explained that teachers are required to have a four-year bachelor's or diploma academic qualifications, pedagogical competencies, personality competencies, social competencies, professional competencies, educator certificates, physically and mentally healthy, and have the ability to realize national education goals. Furthermore, in Article 7 of the Law, it is explained that the teaching profession is a special work carried out based on the principle of having a commitment to improve the quality of education, faith, piety and noble character. The three articles emphasize that professional teachers must have the principles of organizational commitment, academic qualifications, competencies, and responsibilities as the basis for being able to carry out work effectively and efficiently.

In accordance with this opinion Rusman stated the characteristics of professional teachers are: 1) having a commitment in the interests of students and learning; 2) mastering in depth the teaching material, and the use of learning methods and strategies; 3) able to think systematically and always learn from experience, want self-reflection, and correction; 4) the teaching and learning process is getting better; 5) responsible for monitoring and observing student behavior through evaluation activities, applications in the classroom and making analysis evaluation programs, remedial, and carrying out guidance.

Based on the explanation above, a school principal, teacher, who is professional must have a commitment in the management of good education, this is evidenced by a strong desire to maintain the quality and quality of education, acceptance and goals of effective school management.

With regard to school management in the context of realizing national education goals as stipulated in Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning National Education System Chapter II Article 3 states that: National education functions to develop capabilities and shape the dignified character and civilization of the nation in the context of developing the intellectual life of the nation, aiming at developing the potential of students to become human beings who believe in and fear God Almighty, have noble, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and be a democratic and responsible citizen.

When confronted with globalization competition, the government needs to prepare superior human resources who are seen to be able to provide hope to change a better life in the future. Likewise, in order to obtain superior human resources, naturally superior schools which are managed effectively and efficiently need to be prepared.

2.2. Effective Schools

Effective school is a school that humanizes humans in the sense of respecting every potential that exists in students. Furthermore, West Java said that an effective school is defined as the same as an effective school which is a school that has the ability to organize processes and produce an educational output that is higher than existing standards.

Meanwhile, according to Syafaruddin, effective schools are schools that have results through good inputs, processes and outputs, in which management and leadership are found that are able to direct all school resources in the interests of achieving school goals, there is job satisfaction of personnel,

and qualified graduates and directing school change in an antisifative and productive manner. The same thing was conveyed by Myers and Reed with the concept of The Intelligent School, which concluded from the results of empirical studies on school effectiveness, that smart schools manage several intelligences comprehensively related and inseparable as set out in the table regarding concepts, principles of nine intelligences.

This is in line with what was delivered by Supardi, that effective schools are schools that produce high academic achievement of students, use resources carefully, the existence of a school climate that supports quality learning activities, the satisfaction of every element in the school, and school output can be useful for the environment.

At present effective schools are seen as an effective form of education to improve the quality of education, the quality of human resources. Through the implementation of effective schools, it is expected to produce superior human beings, so that every new school year effective schools are always flooded with public interest to enroll their children in effective schools.

In an effort to improve the quality of national education in stages, planned, measured, the government has developed, and at the same time built an education quality control system through three integrated programs, namely national education standards, education unit accreditation, and education quality assurance.

Specifically relating to accreditation is intended as a form of accountability to the public, relating to the feasibility and performance of the implementation of education in the education program unit whose assessment refers to the implementation of 8 components of national education standards (curriculum standards, process standards, graduate competency standards, assessment standards, standards educators and education personnel, facilities and infrastructure standards, management standards, and financing standards). Schools that have been and have been accredited or not accredited both public and private schools at every level and type of education indicate that the school can and does not issue diplomas, certificates, and the like.

Effective school has been defined as one in which students progress further than might be expected from consideration of its intake. An effective school thus adds extra value to its students' outcomes, in comparison with other schools serving similar intakes. In order to assess value added, measures of individual students' prior attainment are needed to provide a baseline against which subsequent progress can be assessed.

According to the Ministry of National Education in Nur Efendi explained, schools are said to be good if they have eight criteria: (1) students who enter are strictly selected and can be accounted for based on academic achievement, psychological testing and physical tests; (2) educational facilities and infrastructure are met and conducive to the learning process, (3) the climate and atmosphere support for learning activities, (4) teachers and education personnel have high professionalism and adequate levels of welfare, (5) improvising the curriculum to meet the needs of students who generally have a high learning motivation compared to students of his age, (6) student hours of learning are generally longer due to the demands of the curriculum and student learning needs, (7) the learning process is more quality and can be accountable to students and guardians of students, and (8) effective schools benefit the environment.

In line with the Ministry of National Education criteria above, according to experts, schools are said to be effective if they have the following criteria: (1) Aspects of students; the quality of graduates is recognized by other institutions with the following indications: student test scores above the average group of other students; teachers and students work hard to succeed; students are satisfied with their school; students who are referred for mental health services are low even compared to other schools; students win sports competitions and other extra activities; many students study foreign, art and physical languages. (2) Teacher aspects: teachers plan lessons adequately: teacher members are adequate for students; teacher members work together, share ideas, and help one another between them; teacher turnover is low; low teacher conflict. (3) Institutional activities: the school has a national and religious holiday celebration program; extracurricular programs that appeal to students; high moral institutions. (4) Parents receive the results of their children's studies well; parents have the choice to send their children to effective schools compared to other schools.

In general, effective schools have advantages in input (students and instrumental input), teaching and learning processes, and outputs (learning outcomes) shown by multiple intelligences. School residents understand, appreciate, and practice the school as a system so that the work of the school is realized as a result of the collective efforts of the school community. The system consists of a number of components that interact with each other so that teamwork is needed that is compact, intelligent, and dynamic.

Schools have high expectations of student learning achievement, professionalism of educators and education personnel are the focus of attention, effective teaching and learning processes are the focus of school attention, leadership and school management are very professional, the School is responsible for learning outcomes to the public (accountability). The school has a strong learning community. Quality assurance is the commitment of school community members to the public as demonstrated by the quality of the design, implementation and evaluation of School Development Plans (RPS). The school applies the principles of governance (participation, transparency, accountability, etc.), the vision, mission, goals and objectives of the school are shared by the school community, the school implements a learning organization.

Effective school aims to produce educational outputs that have advantages in: (1) basic quality which includes the power of thought, heart power, and physical power, (2) the instrumental quality which includes the mastery of knowledge (soft and hard including its application, namely technology, communication skills, etc., and (3) ability to compete and cooperate with other nations.

In addition, effective schools are also intended to prepare students to have the ability / key competencies to face the era of regionalization / globalization, namely: (1) having a strong and broad basic ability, (2) able to collect, analyze, and use data and information , (3) able to communicate ideas and information. Effective school development must be carried out collectively so it needs to involve stakeholders in education, both politicians, bureaucrats (especially the District / City Education Office), academics, practitioners, community leaders, parents of students, and so on.

Speaking about the nature of the development of science, the 1945 Constitution actually mandates a direction for the development of science and technology as stipulated in article 31 paragraph 5. The article states that the government advances science and technology by upholding religious values and national unity for the advancement of civilization and welfare of humanity.

Based on this, the pattern of development of science in essence has obtained a clear framework, namely the pattern of development of science and technology that still has and upholds religious values, not vice versa contrary to religion. So that eventually gave birth to students who have religious behavior. Concrete steps to shape and familiarize religious behavior in educational institutions, according to Muhaimin, are at three levels, namely the level of values adopted, the level of daily practice, and the level of cultural symbols.

At the level of values adopted, it is necessary to formulate the agreed religious values together, need to be developed in educational institutions, to further build commitment and mutual loyalty among all members of educational institutions towards the agreed values. At this stage consistency is also needed to carry out the agreed values and requires the competence of people who formulate values to give examples of how to apply and manifest religious values in daily activities, so as to form Islamic religious behavior.

In the level of daily practice, the agreed religious values are manifested in the form of daily attitudes and behavior by all school members. The development process can be carried out through three stages, namely: 1) the socialization of agreed religious values as ideal attitudes and behaviors to be achieved in the future in educational institutions; 2) the stipulation of weekly or monthly action plans as stages and systematic steps to be carried out by all parties in educational institutions that realize the agreed religious values; 3) giving awards to the achievements of the citizens of educational institutions, such as teachers, education personnel, and students as an effort to habituate (habit formation) that upholds attitudes and behaviors that are committed and loyal to the teachings and religious values agreed. Appreciation does not always mean material (economic), but also in the social, cultural, psychological or other sense.

In the formation of religious behavior students need to instill a level of cultural symbols that are religious in nature, the development that needs to be done is to replace cultural symbols that are less in line with religious teachings and values with religious cultural symbols. Changes in symbols can be done by changing the model of dress with the principle of closing genitalia, installation of students' work, photographs and mottoes that contain messages of religious value. At the level of this cultural symbol, the formation of religious behavior through habituation seen and enjoyed in everyday life. This of course requires a strategy, both bottom up and top down. Without the right strategy, the formation of religious behavior will experience obstacles, even resistance.

Normative foundation as mentioned above must be used as a reference frame in the development of science, especially in this country. Related to this problem national education must strive to make religious values as core values for all subjects developed in schools. So, it is not science that is barren of religious values as characterized by modern science. The development of science with religious nuances such as this must be interpreted as the embodiment of the 1945 Constitution, and in turn will form humans who have a steady religious behavior and increasingly have faith and

piety. That is, through the mastery of science and habituation of religious behavior obtained will strengthen his faith in God Almighty, and not vice versa farther from his God.

3. Conclusion

Professional teacher management in schools is effective based on a literature review by the author, that is, a teacher who is professional in carrying out management, taking into account all tasks, functions and authorities so that it becomes a culture that is applied in schools. The ongoing process makes the school more effective in every learning activity available. The characteristics of professional teachers, namely: (1) have a commitment to organizational culture or commitment to the learning process of students; (2) mastering in depth the subject matter and how to teach it; (3) able to think systematically about what is done and learn from experience; and (4) is a part of learning societies from their professional environment that enables them to improve their professionalism.

Implementation of effective schools, not only one type of intelligence is the target of the focus of attention, but there are various other intelligences that are inseparable to be considered, so that in effective school management will involve all elements. Human resources in the education unit environment to bring forth the growth of a continuous learning culture for students, educators, and education staff.

Effective schools are synonymous with smart schools because in the end the result of treatment while attending teaching and learning activities is to produce the best graduates, who not only have adequate knowledge but also behave actively, creatively, innovatively, independently and have good character. In the concept of effective school, it is expected that schools that continuously improve their performance and use their resources optimally to develop and develop student achievement as a whole, are not only able to foster academic achievement of students, but are able to develop abilities, skills and other potentials that students have. Hopefully this article is useful.

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*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: sumarto.manajemeno@gmail.com